

ONE4ALL PROJECT

PERIODIC UPDATE ON OUR ACTIVITIES

Project ONE4ALL benefits from Horizon Results Booster service

The success of a project often hinges not just on groundbreaking ideas but also on effective dissemination and exploitation of results. For this reason, Horizon Europe is providing an invaluable service to amplify the impact of research projects: the Horizon Results Booster (HRB).

It provides tailored support to maximize the dissemination and exploitation of project results. The Consortium of ONE4ALL recognises the potential of this service and decided to implement some of its functionalities within the project lifecycle.

At the moment, [EXELISIS](#) is coordinating the efforts of partners towards the collection of inputs and information; ONE4ALL Consortium is using the HRB service for extra-complementary support expanding the existing dissemination/exploitation potential of the ONE4ALL project as a whole. In addition to EXELISIS (manager of exploitation), also [IDENER](#) and [INNOGLOBAL](#) are involved in this activity as technical partners.

For more information on Horizon Results Booster, visit <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

ONE4ALL Project at MECSPE 2024

On March 7th, ONE4ALL has been mentioned from [AUTOMATIONWARE](#) (technology provider of the consortium) at the MECSPE fair in Bologna.

During the Solution Award event, the participants had the opportunity to present an innovative technology solution developed: AUTOMATIONWARE presented a prototype application for automatized end of line activities.

The main goals of the application are:

- Development of a flexible and efficient solution, which can facilitate the work of operators.
- Robot reconfiguration, according to production needs.
- Implementation of a centralized software control of a heterogeneous robotic system for process productivity optimization.

Figure 1: slide from AUTOMATIONWARE presentation

Campi di utilizzo

Campi di utilizzo:

- Health and Food: il sistema può essere proposto sia nel campo farmaceutico che alimentare per attività di fine linea (ad es. prelievo, pallettizzazione, bin picking).

Agile and modular cyber-physical technologies supported by data-driven digital tools to reinforce manufacturing resilience

The project aims to boost manufacturing plants' transformation towards Industry 5.0, reinforcing their resilience under unexpected changes in social needs. It is done through self-reconfigurable mobile collaborative robots embedded with IIOT devices for real-time monitoring and interconnectivity.

Duration 48 Months	Work plan 7 WPs	Budget € 5.999.206,25
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The collaborative robots will be tested in two relevant environments, belonging to sectors needing more flexibility as a consequence of greater fluctuations:

agri-food
 pharmaceutical

ONE4ALL Joins the ENGINE Initiative

To increase the network and appeal of ONE4ALL project, in 2023 the partners have decided to join the ENGINE Initiative: <http://www.engineinitiative.eu/>

The ENGINE Initiative (European Network for Global Innovation in New Energy) is a dynamic network that brings together leading research projects, industry stakeholders, and policymakers to accelerate the development and deployment of new energy solutions. By facilitating knowledge exchange and collaboration, ENGINE aims to address global energy challenges and promote a sustainable energy future.

ONE4ALL participation has been announced in the latest newsletter, which is available online here

You can also subscribe to receive the newsletter via email on the Initiative website homepage.

Want to know more about the project?

More details on the project activities, results, consortium are available on the official website: <https://one4allproject.eu/>

To remain updated, follow ONE4ALL social medias: [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)